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Wildfire Threat, Mitigation, Risk Transfer and Insurability: Texas and the Western US

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KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

Wildfire risk in the US and around the world has increased dramatically in recent years. In the US, the western states including Montana, Washington, Oregon, and California have been most impacted. Texas has now become a hot spot for wildfires with significant losses as well. Risk transfer has been traditionally through insurance and dependent on community funded responses. However, due to staggering losses, the insurance community has chosen to non-renew policies throughout the western states and in Texas, significantly impacting the health and wellbeing of communities and individuals. Mitigation from wildfire risk is possible and should be a common practice in the at-risk states. Communities and individuals can reduce fuel load on properties, create safety zones around structures, manage sources of human caused ignition, use fire resistant building materials, and ensure rapid and effective response resources are available. Insurability is becoming more difficult causing home and business owners to rely on default state or federal programs as the last means of risk transfer. Vulnerable communities are especially impacted with options too expensive to engage leaving many uninsured and/or underinsured. New strategies are needed to provide asset protection. The National Flood Protection Program serves as an encouraging model to address the growing wildfire risk in the west and Texas. This type of program would require communities and individuals to be more engaged in all phases of wildfire management. Stakeholders would be partners in cohesive planning, mitigation, response and recovery. The challenges are significant and this paper provides an overview of the wildfire threat, insurability, mitigation strategies, and program alternatives.

1. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Wildfires have increased significantly in the US and globally (Zhang et al., 2022). The impacts to humans, animals and the environment have been devastating (Cunningham, Williamson & Bowman, 2024). Australia's wildfire in 2019-2020 claimed an estimated 2.8 billion vertebrates and decimated 116 plant species in the fire ravaged area. Asia's fires were associated with more than 100,000 premature deaths due to air pollution with an estimated economic impact of over \$16

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billion (Cunningham, Williamson & Bowman, 2024). Satellite images over a 20-year period from 2003 to 2023 show a 2.2-fold increase in wildfires around the world, see Figure 1

Figure 1

Extreme Wildfire Events 2003 – 2023

Source: Cunningham, C. X., Williamson, G. J., & Bowman, D. M. (2024). Increasing frequency and intensity of the most extreme wildfires on Earth. Nature Ecology & Evolution, 8(8), 1420-1425

The frequency and intensity of wildfires have increased exponentially. Increasing aridity associated with climate change has been the major driver of fires in the western US between 1979 to 2015 (Abatzoglou & Williams, 2016). Over the past four decades, wildfires have quadrupled their devastation in the US (Burke et al., 2021). In January 2025, Southern California was impacted by several wildfires that burned into the greater Los Angeles area causing devastating impacts. The Palisades and Eaton Fires both burned uncontrolled into heavily populated areas, ultimately claiming the lives of 29 individuals and destroying thousands of homes and businesses (MacCarthy & Richter, 2025). In the months prior to the destructive firestorm, many residents within the impacted areas were forced to seek new homeowners' insurance (MacCarthy & Richter, 2025). The situation was due to insurance companies within California non-renewing policies for homes located in high wildfire risk areas. The strategy was intended to reduce the insurance company's financial risk. This type of business decision has become a common strategy for insurance companies to insulate investments from the growing list of wildfire disasters with a high number of claims requiring payout (MacCarthy & Richter, 2025). While this issue may seem limited to California, it is occurring across the United States in areas prone to wildfires.

As communities expand into adjacent rural areas, homes are built on landscapes that have historically had frequent wildfires. Urban expansion into what is known as the Wildland Urban Interface (WUI) classifies homes as those at greater risk of being impacted by wildfire (Jones et al., 2011). In response to the growing threat, insurance companies elect non-renewal policies, or in many cases, deny coverage for new policies due to the homes being in a high wildfire risk area and their potential payout. While areas within California, Colorado, and Montana are known for their wildfires, Texas has come to the forefront by having numerous areas with high wildfire risk as well.

In the summer of 2024, the Austin, TX news station KVUE released a segment highlighting several communities around Austin that were being impacted by the same strategy (Sanchez, 2024). The article highlighted several homeowners who live adjacent to the Balcones Canyonland Preserve, an area known to protect the endangered Golden-Cheeked Warbler and the now delisted, Black Capped Vireo. Due to

the wildfire risk from these protected habitat lands, insurance companies opted not to renew homeowners existing policies. While the practice of non-renewal for wildfire threat is a recent problem for Texas, it has been a common issue for residents of the Gulf Coast for years. Texas Monthly highlighted the growing struggles many homeowners face with obtaining and maintaining coverage for homes along the hurricane-prone coast (Hardy, 2024). With the issue now expanding to impact inland communities, what resources are available to residents, and what are the potential long-term solutions?

2. INSURANCE REGULATIONS AND UNDERWRITING

Severe weather events, such as hurricanes and floods, pose a significant risk to homes located in these disaster-prone areas. This is especially true within Texas, where the Gulf Coast is known for its hurricanes. Recently, however, there has been a growing impact on homeowners who reside inland within areas deemed as “high risk” for wildfires. If an insurance company determines that a home has high potential for damage or loss due to a specific type of disaster, the policy may be non-renewed. A non-renewal is the equivalent of being dropped by a carrier, forcing a homeowner to seek other options. In most cases, the homeowner will be unable to obtain another policy due to the risk and will be forced to utilize a last-resort coverage. Questions are often raised regarding how and why insurance companies manage their policies in this way. This can be answered by reviewing the insurance industry and how each company manages risk in its portfolio of insureds structures.

Within the United States, Insurance companies are regulated at the state level (NAIC, 2011). This state-level regulation is traced back to the 19th century, with the McCarran-Ferguson Act of 1945 clarifying that “states should regulate and tax the business of insurance” (NAIC, 2011). This regulation ensures that insurance companies comply with all required standards to operate within a given state. While states may vary regarding specific regulations, issuing policies and managing risk to a company’s portfolio is standard. When an individual inquires about coverage with a company, the insurance agency reviews data for the individual and properties being covered in a process called underwriting.

Underwriting is used to evaluate the financial risk associated with a policy. The underwriting process is broken down into six functional areas: 1) Objective Analysis, 2) Risk Assessment, 3) Insurance Tariff Calculation, 4) Insurance Premium Calculation, 5) Negotiating the Franchise, and 6) Negotiating the Insurance Amount (Narzullaevich, 2022). Our focus is on the risk assessment process.

During the risk assessment process, an underwriter focuses on identifying any potential risk of losses a policy could bring to the insurer. This includes financial risk due to the individual themselves or the property (Narzullaevich, 2022). Risk due to potential claims associated with the property includes an evaluation of any noted threats that could result in damage or loss of the property. While this is a broad category, areas with well-known threats, such as weather-related events, are easier to evaluate due to available data. The underwriter utilizes data on known risks along with documented claims within the area to assess the overall risk of the policy (Narzullaevich, 2022). At that point, a policy will either move forward to cost determination or be denied. This process is also completed during a policy renewal evaluation period.

3. WILDFIRE RISK

Each year, the underwriting process eliminates properties from eligibility due to the risk associated with the coverage. This has been a known issue along the Gulf coast of Texas, where property losses have been significant and risk is deemed high associated with hurricanes and coastal flooding.

Within California, insurance companies have been denying and non-renewing policies for wildfire danger and associated risk of losses for years. While the issue of insurance non-renewal for wildfire threat in Texas is relatively new, the data shows that home loss due to wildfires in Texas has been a consistent and growing problem. According to a report by the Texas A&M Forest Service, 2011 was one of the most destructive wildfire years recorded for the state. Over 31,000 wildfires were reported, resulting in over 4 million acres being burned and 2,947 homes destroyed (Jones et al., 2012) with costs estimated at \$505 million (NOAA, 2011), see Figure 2.

Figure 2

Texas Wildfires 2011

Source: Texas A&M Forest Service. (2025). Texas Wildfire Risk Explorer. TXWRAP. <https://wrap.texaswildfirerisk.com/page 10>

While many wildfires burned throughout 2011, the report highlighted several notable fires that resulted in a high number of homes destroyed or damaged. Four significant wildfires included: 1) Rockhouse Fire in Jeff Davis and Presidio Counties, resulting in 23 homes being destroyed; 2) the Possum Kingdom Complex in Palo Pinto, Young, and Stevens Counties, resulting in 168 homes destroyed; 3) the Bastrop Complex Fire in Bastrop County resulting in 1,660 homes destroyed; and finally, 4) the Riley Road Fire in Montgomery, Grimes, and Waller Counties, resulting in 73 homes destroyed.

Since 2011, Texas has continued to experience high impacts from wildfires that result in property damage and loss. In January of 2024, the Texas Panhandle was impacted by the Smokehouse Creek Fire, which burned over 1.2 million acres in Texas and Oklahoma destroying over 100 homes and businesses (Asch, 2025). All the fires are the result of conditions that could be evaluated to determine an area's fire risk utilizing a publicly available rating system. The National Fire Danger Rating System (NFDRS) is utilized by underwriters to determine potential risks to a property from wildfires.

For wildfire to propagate, there must be three key elements in place as outlined in the fire triangle: Fuel, Heat, and Oxygen (NWCG, 2025). The most consistent of the three elements is fuel. Fuel is characterized as any grass, brush, timber, and slash that is consumed during the combustion of the fire and directly relates to fire behavior (NWCG, 2025). Since fuel is a constant on the landscape, it is easy to map and categorize into groups known as “fuel models.” Fuel models are utilized to determine fire behavior at specific sites on the landscape, utilizing mathematical models (Anderson, 1982). This means that the more grass, brush, and trees that are adjacent to a structure, the more likely it is to be impacted by high-intensity fire. Ultimately, insurance companies interpret these circumstances as increased exposure, risk, and probable losses due to wildfires.

While fuels are relatively consistent, weather and ignition sources are dynamically changing. Modeling fire risk assumes weather conditions are conducive to wildfire spread and extreme behavior. Ignition modeling is based on historical data that captures every wildfire that has been responded to by organized resources. If a property is adjacent to an area that historically has had numerous wildfires, it would be at greater risk of being impacted by wildfire within any given year. This type of information has become easier to access due to open-source data, such as the Texas Wildfire Risk Explorer (2025). Individuals within any area of Texas can quickly assess the threat to their home from potential wildfires to identify their perceived risk. Since fuel is the most constant variable in determining fire behavior, they are one of the easiest inputs that can be altered to reduce risk; resulting in a more insurable home and being less prone to damage or loss in a disaster.

4. WILDFIRE MITIGATION STRATEGIES

Coordinated wildfire mitigation strategies became a reality after the Federal Land Assistance, Management, and Enhancement Act of 2009 (FLAME Act) was passed by congress (US Forest Service, 2014). The three-phase cohesive program established national goals. The FLAME Act required that the Nation address the broad challenges including managing vegetation/fuels; protecting homes, communities, and other values at risk; managing human-caused ignitions; and effectively and efficiently responding to wildfires (US Forest Service, 2014). The FLAME Act provided general guidance for designing and prioritizing fuel treatments; strategically placing fuel treatments; increasing use of wildland fire for meeting resource objectives. The act supported expanding methods to improve the resiliency across the nation. The next priority focused on engaging homeowners and communities in taking proactive steps prior to wildfires to mitigate risk and losses. Next, the act emphasized programs and activities tailored to address local needs in preventing human-caused fires. Lastly, the plan aimed to safely and effectively extinguish fires, use fire to mitigate risk when and where allowable, manage natural resources, and support safe strategies to coexist with wildland fires (US Forest Service, 2014). The vision, goals and challenges from the National Cohesive Management Strategy are seen in Figure 3.

One of the most effective methods to reduce the severity of wildfire risk has been the practice of using prescribed burns that reduce fuel loads. This method is both effective and cost-efficient. Prescribed burns reduce wildfire hazards by decreasing available fuel vegetation. They also support ecosystem restoration, maintenance and silviculture (US Forest Service, 2014). The focus was placed on five key factors associated with wildfire, see figure 2. Fundamentally, controlled fires are particularly effective tools for areas with fire-adapted or fire-dependent vegetation and a history of wildfire (US Fire Service, 2014).

Figure 3
National Cohesive Management Strategy

Source: US Forest Service. (2014). National cohesive wildland fire management strategy. Access June 11, 2025 <https://www.fs.usda.gov/restoration/cohesivestrategy.shtml> page 6

Figure 4
Five Key Factors Associated with Wildfire Mitigation, Response and Management.

Source: US Forest Service. (2014). National cohesive wildland fire management strategy. Access June 11, 2025 <https://www.fs.usda.gov/restoration/cohesivestrategy.shtml> page 25

Additional non-fire methods are also used to reduce fuel hazards. Common strategies include using mechanical devices such as equipment for thinning and disposal of vegetation and debris. Additionally, livestock grazing can be used to reduce fuels in rangeland areas. Less desirable methods may also include using herbicides to eliminate and/or control vegetation (US forest Service, 2014).

Wildfire prevention and protection begins with proper zoning, careful planning and cautious expansion into the WUI (Reams et al., 2005). An estimated 1/3 of all homes are located in the WUI (Lee, Ma & Li, 2022). Communities proximate to WUI should develop Community Wildfire Protection Plans that include researching the wildfire history in the area, mapping the topography, use of fuel and vegetation maps, research about the demographics of the areas and identifying at-risk individuals, proper risk assessment, and an action plan for mitigation and response (USFA, 2025). Areas with high risk of wildfires should include coordinated mitigation strategies with involvement of all stakeholders (US Forest Service, 2014).

Community actions to reduce risks for wildfires may include the installation of fire break zones in hazardous areas (Lee, Ma & Li, 2022). Adhering to building codes are important especially those that require fire resistant materials be used in homes and businesses (Reams et al., 2001; US forest Service, 2014). The NFPA 299 is an example of such a code that provides standards to reduce wildfire risk by recommending proper risk assessment of property and structure, defensible zones by keeping vegetation 30' to 100' from structures, proper building design and materials, community planning and action (NFPA, 1997).

Despite push back, community residents should engage effective management practices to reduce fuel loads (Reams et al., 2005). Working collectively is more effective than recommending individuals take independent action. However, landowners may be reluctant to commit resources to an event that they feel is uncontrollable (Reams et al., 2005). Generally speaking, ordinances aimed at controlling vegetation are not well accepted. Property owners prefer to do as they wish with their property and not be told what vegetation is preferred or its location in proximity to structure (Reams, et al., 2005). Residents often reject recommendations to remove vegetation in proximity to their home pointing to negative valuation as one major reason. Prior research revealed that citizens prefer to believe that technology would protect their property in the event of wildfire (Mileti & Peek-Gottschlich, 2001).

The public is willing to accept education on the topic and the right to choose mitigation strategies (Reams et al., 2001). Educational initiatives have been expanding and successful across the US. Many forms of education include demonstration gardens, public events and meetings, newspapers, radio and television broadcasts (Reams et al., 2005). Property owners are taught the importance of hazard reduction and home hardening through thinning vegetation and creating fire protection and safety zones around their homes and structures. Other successful programs have included public assistance such as free home and property inspections, free clearing and chipping of debris as well as cost-share programs that support similar services (Reams, et al., 2001). The most common approach to wildfire protection is transfer of risk via insurance however, this is becoming more difficult in fire prone area across the nation, especially in the west and now in Texas leading to underinsurance and non-renewal challenges.

5. UNDERINSURANCE

Insurance companies utilize the underwriting process to evaluate the financial risk of their policies. With the increasing number of wildfires that result in numerous home losses, the financial risk to these companies has been amplified. While the risk associated with the environment in which the home is built has a direct effect on risk, there are additional factors that influence financial risk. One of those being rising construction costs, especially following a significant disaster. In the article “The Unnatural Disaster of Insurance, Underinsurance, and Natural Disasters”, Klein (2023) assessed numerous fires across the United States that resulted in home loss to determine insurance coverage and shortfalls. Upon review of California’s Camp Fire that burned through the city of Paradise in 2018, it was determined that

the average cost to rebuild a lost home far exceeded the coverage most insurance policies provided. Following the Camp Fire, Merced Property and Casualty underwent financial hardship, resulting in the seizure and liquidation of the company by California (Boyett & Yan, 2018). Since insurance is regulated at the state level, California handled the liquidation of an insurance company and the settlement of any claims through the guarantor as needed (Boyett & Yan, 2018).

While the issue may seem specific to California, Klein (2023), evaluated the central Texas fires of 2011 and reported that 56% of individual owners had an average underinsured cost of \$110,000. The author reported that this trend continued throughout all the disasters that he reviewed (Klein, 2023). Further research in Colorado by the Department of Insurance noted that the average baseline cost to rebuild is \$250 per square foot with only 35% of policies being underwritten to cover these costs (Auer & Hexamer, 2022). As the baseline cost to reconstruct a home increased, the percentage of uninsured policies also increased, with 67% of all policies being insufficient at a rebuild cost of \$350 per square foot (Auer & Hexamer, 2022). This means that insurance companies are paying the maximum amount on at least 30% of all claims per disaster.

6. THE FAIR RISK TRANSFER PLAN

Insurance companies are denying the renewal of policies within high-risk areas instead of increasing rates, which are also capped under state regulation (Hardy, 2024). Once denied or dropped, homeowners must seek last resort insurance coverage. Some mortgage companies offer these types of policies to their customers. A last resort policy may also be obtained through a state-run Fair Access to Insurance Requirements (FAIR) Plan. In 1968, California developed the first FAIR Plan following a series of wildfire outbreaks that affected communities around the Los Angeles area (Kousky et al., 2019). A FAIR Plan is the last resort of insurance option for residents who cannot find a carrier on the open market. All insurance companies licensed to operate within California must participate in the state's FAIR Plan. Any policies issued through the FAIR Plan are randomly assigned to a carrier from the pool of all participating insurance companies that operate in the state (About FAIR Plan, 2024). This process of random policy assignment ensures that the risk associated with the FAIR Plan Policies is shared evenly across all insurance companies.

Currently, Texas is one of 35 states that offers a FAIR Plan as a last resort of insurance. Unlike California, the Texas FAIR Plan Association (TFPA) manages all issued policies through the voluntary market and does not rely on primary carriers (Coverage & Eligibility, 2024). Applicants to TFPA must meet eligibility requirements, including at least two declinations from insurers. This framework provides a last resort of insurance for homeowners within the state of Texas, with most current policies being issued along the Gulf Coast for flood and hurricane threat (Coverage & Eligibility, 2024). One noted issue with this type of coverage is that premiums are higher than open market options but are still below the premium amount needed to cover a policy payout for home loss. This can create a false market based on artificially low premiums that do not reflect the actual risk to a home (Lueck and Bradshaw, 2012). They also fail to account for the elevated costs to repair or rebuild following a disaster. This issue can compound the financial impacts to a FAIR Plan if a disaster results in the loss of a high number of homes utilizing these policies. Following the Palisades and Eaton Fires, the California FAIR Plan required a \$1 billion bailout from the insurance companies that operate within the California market (Ma, 2025). This funding was needed for the FAIR Plan to settle all payouts for policies affected by the fires.

As a result of the government regulated bailout, insurance companies have received approval to enact an emergency rate increase (Ma, 2025). One of the largest carriers, State Farm Insurance Company, received preliminary approval for an increase of 22% after stating, “the multibillion-dollar payouts in the Los Angeles area would threaten its balance sheet and the broader market” (MA, 2025). Another option for insurers’ response to these growing threats is to cease operations within the state. In his doctoral dissertation, Dr. Almuhan (2024) notes that insurance companies’ withdrawal from California markets are a direct result of disaster related losses, financial risk and limitations to adjust rates to offset impacts to portfolios in the event of a future disaster. Since the FAIR Plan is comprised of companies operating within the California market, there is still some risk of a high number of payouts from a disaster to private companies. The sustainability of the FAIR Plan is then brought into question if events like the Paradise Fire or Palisades Fires are becoming far more common.

7. RISK TO VULNERABLE POPULATIONS

The process of dropping insured homes and business owners is becoming a more common practice by insurance companies when evaluation of wildfire risk is high and unfairly impacting vulnerable populations (Klein, 2025). Evaluation of the insurability due to wildfire risk shows a disproportionate risk to low-income populations (Auer & Hexamer, 2022). This relationship between risk and low-income was identified through an analysis of counties within the United States with the highest wildfire risk compared to the county poverty level. The findings highlighted those areas with the highest wildfire risk also had higher poverty rates (Auer & Hexamer, 2022). This correlation was consistent for numerous states, including California and Texas. With an established relationship between wildfire risk and insurance non-renewal, lower-income populations are at a higher risk of being adversely affected. This is mainly due to low-income families' inability to pay higher coverage rates, including those of the FAIR Plan. These individuals are also less likely to have the means to recover from a disaster on their own. With the noted increased rebuilding costs, homeowners who lack insurance or are underinsured must rely on FEMA for assistance during a disaster.

8. FEDERAL FEMA PROGRAMS

Meant as a last resort of assistance, the FEMA Individual Assistance program assists those affected by a federally declared disaster who lack insurance or are substantially underinsured (Webster, 2025). While this program serves the vulnerable populations impacted by a disaster, the cost of any payout is deferred to taxpayers through FEMA (Webster, 2025). FEMA’s Individual Assistance program was not designed to replace primary insurance and is only available for communities impacted by a disaster that receive a Federal Disaster Declaration (Webster, 2025). FEMA also manages the National Flood Insurance Program (NFIP) to provide an affordable flood insurance option for residents who would otherwise be unable to obtain a policy (Liao et al., 2024). The NFIP offers policies for flood insurance that are sold through private companies and underwritten by the federal government. The NFIP also coordinates with local governments to ensure that flood zones are correctly delineated and that any residential structures within those areas conform to specific building codes (Liao et al., 2024). The framework for NFIP could be adapted to develop a similar wildfire-type policy. While Liao et al. acknowledge that the framework exists for a wildfire specific policy, there are also some drawbacks. The most notable is the potentially high cost of coverage if prices are set based on evaluated risk (Liao et al., 2024). This would likely compound the issue of disproportionate risk to those in lower socioeconomic areas. There are also numerous benefits, including guaranteed access to coverage and potential mitigation requirements to help reduce home loss. Mitigating high-risk fuel types can directly increase a home's survivability and thus would be justified under the program.

If there were an NFIP type system for wildfire insurance, required mitigation work could be implemented within high-risk fire sheds. While this can create additional restrictions on coverage, it would benefit the overall survivability of a home. This mitigation is done by altering the fuels surrounding a home to reduce potential impact from direct flame contact and firebrands, or embers (Hazra & Gallagher, 2022). By requiring mitigation work in connection with insurance coverage, homeowners must meet mitigation standards to maintain coverage. This is a benefit since it is noted that most homeowners only prioritize mitigation after impacts from a wildfire (Hazra & Gallagher, 2022). The research further highlights that most homeowners prioritize home amenities over wildfire mitigation work. By having a program that holds homeowners accountable, the risk to homes could be managed on a per-home basis. To fully implement this type of program, there would remain the need for federal legislation, similar to the National Flood Insurance Act of 1968.

9. CONCLUSION

The threat from wildfire continues to be a growing risk to communities across the United States as urban areas expand outward. Homes are now built on larger lots in natural areas intermixed with grass, brush, and trees. This expansion has resulted in residential areas with a high risk of being impacted by wildfire. While wildfires have burned on the landscape for decades, those areas were largely unpopulated. With the increase in homes lost during wildland fire incidents, insurance companies must address their portfolio's financial solvency and risk by not insuring at-risk homes. While not all fires cause home loss, incidents like the Bastrop Complex, Camp, and Palisades fires all resulted in thousands of homes lost, requiring numerous policy payouts from insurance companies. As a result, insurance companies now opt to non-renew or deny coverage for homes in high wildfire risk areas.

While denying a policy may protect the insurance company from loss, it increases the homeowner's vulnerability in the event of a disaster. Individuals must then seek a replacement policy on the open market or through their mortgage company. If no coverage is available due to repeated declinations, they may pursue coverage through a FAIR Plan. These policies are managed within each state to provide coverage when no other options exist. These plans often provide minimal coverage for higher rates than open market competitors. However, they often fail to have rates reflecting the risk to all covered structures. This means a false market can be developed, and in the event of a large wildfire, funds may not be available to cover all the payouts. This recently occurred with the Palisades and Eaton Fires, with the California FAIR Plan requiring a \$1 billion bailout. This brings into question the sustainability of these programs with the steady increase of residents needing FAIR Plan coverage, along with the growing frequency of catastrophic fires that impact urban areas.

With the growing reliance on FAIR Plans and the questions regarding the sustainability of the programs, the question then shifts to a need for federal legislation. For federal oversight to occur, legislation would need to be developed similar to that of the National Flood Insurance Act (Liao et al. 2024). This federal program is managed through FEMA and provides flood insurance to homeowners located within a floodplain. The NFIP could be utilized as a model of a potential solution for wildfire insurance and risk transfer. This type of program would come with many challenges, including high policy costs. There are also some noted advantages, like the ability to require wildfire mitigation measures around structures to increase survivability if impacted.

Ultimately, residents are left responsible for seeking coverage and accepting the risk of not having an insurance policy or underinsured coverage levels. Meanwhile, emergency managers face the challenge of responding to residents who are no longer covered due to the risk of the wildland fire. Mitigation

efforts can assist with reducing risk, but are often time-consuming, costly, and only cover small areas on public lands. Homeowners implementing mitigation efforts on their own home is the most valuable option, but is often downplayed by residents as important, even though it could help reduce the chance of losing coverage to their home.

This issue has implications for emergency management and economics. Additional research on this topic is needed to effectively evaluate the nuances of all aspects, including the impacts on a FAIR Plan following multiple high-loss incidents, such as those in California in January 2025. As this issue grows, more data will be available for researchers to fully identify the underlying cause and effect of a problem impacting residents across the United States. The current process utilized by insurance companies to manage financial risk merely shifts the risk back to homeowners. Further research should also focus on oversight that protects homeowners, especially those within vulnerable populations.

AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTIONS

Mr. Steven Moore earned his Associates of Science degree in Homeland Security & Emergency Management and his Bachelors of Science and Arts in Emergency Management at West Texas A&M graduating in 2025. This paper was the central theme for his Senior Capstone project to graduate. He conceived the project and was the primary author for the paper. Dr. Gilkey is a Safety Professional at Montana Technological University interested in the wildfire risk and management and provided additional content to the paper and review for publication.

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Steven Moore earned his Associate of Science degree in Homeland Security & Emergency Management in 2020 and his Bachelor of Science and Arts degree in Emergency Management from West Texas A&M in 2025. Mr. Moore is the Wildfire Manager for Travis County, Texas, USA. Steven has been working for nearly 20 years as a professional in wildfire management and mitigation. He plans and implements prescribed fires on park and conservation lands, including coordination with local jurisdictions and emergency service providers. He coordinates the organizational and operational activities of the parkland management program for Travis County Parks. Mr. Moore also recommends and implements policies and procedures as well as coordinating and reviewing the work plan for assigned land management contracted services and activities. His duties also include prioritizing and specifying contracted work activities and projects. He reviews and evaluates work products, methods, and procedures. Steven represents Travis County Parks at meetings, public events, and with the media. Mr. Steven Moore enjoys educating and conducting presentations to the public to better inform them on wildfire risks and mitigation strategies.

